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Authors:

Name	Partner
Chiara de Tomasso	EAPM
Denis Horgan	EAPM
Sofia Pazzagli	EAPM
Anđela Skarpa	EAPM

Reviewers:

Name	Partner
Manuel Ottaviano	UPM
Lyuba Karpachova	SIOP
Katerina Nikitara	ELLOK

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List of abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
JA PCM	Joint Action Personalised Cancer Medicine
LB	Liquid Biopsy
MTB	Molecular Tumour Board
NGS	Next-Generation Sequencing
PCM	Personalised Cancer Medicine
SCG	Stakeholder Coordination Group
SPARC	Support of Personalised medicine Approaches in Cancer
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholder Engagement Plan of the SPARC project

Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable D9.1 and presents the Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Plan of the SPARC project (Support of Personalised Medicine Approaches in Cancer), an EU4Health action designed to support the implementation of personalised cancer medicine across Europe. The plan defines the strategic framework, objectives, target audiences, messages, channels, and governance mechanisms guiding communication and dissemination activities throughout the project duration.

SPARC addresses key implementation challenges in personalised cancer medicine by advancing coordination and evidence generation related to Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs), liquid biopsy, and disease-specific clinical pilots. In this context, communication and dissemination activities are conceived not only to ensure project visibility, but also to support policy coherence, informed dialogue, and practical uptake of project outputs at EU and Member State level.

The plan adopts a structured, adaptive, and audience-sensitive approach, ensuring that communication activities evolve in line with project milestones, emerging insights, and policy developments. It clearly distinguishes between communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement, while ensuring strong integration among these functions. Internal communication mechanisms support the systematic extraction and synthesis of insights from project activities, which are then translated into external dissemination outputs and policy-relevant formats.

A central feature of the strategy is SPARC's alignment with other relevant EU initiatives and specifically with the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine (JA PCM). Communication and dissemination activities are designed to reinforce coherence across initiatives, avoid duplication, and position SPARC as a complementary and enabling action within the European cancer policy landscape.

This Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Plan combines an overall strategic vision aligned with the Grant Agreement's action-level indicators with a detailed and adaptive implementation plan for the first 18 months of the project.

Overall, the plan provides a coherent, policy-oriented, and implementation-focused framework that supports SPARC's contribution to advancing personalised cancer medicine in Europe.

1. Introduction

SPARC (Support of Personalized medicine Approaches in Cancer) is an EU4Health action that addresses key challenges in implementing personalised cancer medicine across Europe by advancing diagnostics, improving access to care, and supporting better outcomes across high-incidence and rare cancers through a set of coordinated pilot activities and implementation-focused work packages.

This Communication and Dissemination Plan defines the **strategic approach through which SPARC communicates its role, progress, and outputs, and disseminates insights, syntheses, and recommendations** emerging from the project. It is conceived with a flexible and adaptive approach, allowing communication and dissemination activities to respond to evolving policy priorities, implementation milestones, and emerging needs over the course of the project.

SPARC is designed to contribute to synergies with Member State strategies and related EU initiatives and it is naturally aligned with the pillars of the Joint Action on Personalised Medicine (JA PCM). In this context, SPARC acts as an enabling and preparatory action within the European personalised cancer medicine landscape, generating implementation-relevant evidence and coordination insights that can inform and support EU-level initiatives. Communication and dissemination activities are therefore designed not only to ensure visibility, but also to facilitate coherence, policy relevance, and practical uptake of SPARC outputs.

This document provides the strategic framework for the implementation of communication activities under Task 9.4, including the development and maintenance of the project website, the use of digital and media channels, the production of dissemination materials, and communication activities linked to project milestones, workshops, and policy-oriented outputs. It supports the achievement of the key action-level indicators defined in the GA and complements SPARC's wider policy outreach and coordination efforts, including planned work on synergies with the JA PCM.

The first part of this plan focuses on communication and dissemination activities, and covers:

- the objectives of SPARC's communication and dissemination efforts;
- the key audiences addressed;
- the core messages and narratives conveyed;
- the channels and formats used to ensure visibility and dissemination;

- the mechanisms for monitoring effectiveness.

Stakeholder engagement activities are covered in a dedicated chapter, which describes the structures, processes, and formats through which stakeholder input is collected, discussed, and consolidated within SPARC.

The separation between communication and dissemination on the one hand, and stakeholder engagement on the other, reflects SPARC's methodological approach. While stakeholder engagement activities generate input, perspectives, and consensus, communication and dissemination activities ensure that resulting outputs are synthesised, contextualised, and communicated in a coherent and policy-relevant manner. Together, the two plans form complementary components of SPARC's overall approach to supporting policy coordination and implementation.

The plan follows a deliberate progression: first describing how insights are generated and shared internally within SPARC (Chapter 3); then outlining how these insights are communicated externally (Chapter 4); and finally explaining how communication and stakeholder engagement are structured to support governance, coordination, and policy uptake, including alignment with the JA PCM (Chapter 5).

1.2. Identity and SPARC logo

To ensure recognition, coherence, and a consistent visual presentation across all communication and dissemination activities, SPARC uses a dedicated visual identity defined in an official project brand book. The brand book establishes the core visual elements of the project, including the SPARC logo, colour palette and typography.

The SPARC logo draws inspiration from the *Star of Life*, the internationally recognised symbol of healthcare, which is reinterpreted as a stylised human figure. This design **conveys care, support, unity, and movement, reflecting SPARC's mission to advance personalised cancer care through collaboration and innovation.** The dynamic form suggests progress and continuous development, while the modern, clean typography ensures clarity, accessibility, and professional consistency across all communication outputs.

Figure 1: SPARC project logo

The SPARC brand book is shared with all consortium partners through the project's internal communication channels and serves as the reference document for the preparation of all SPARC communication and dissemination materials. The application of the SPARC visual identity within the project website is further described in Deliverable D9.5, ensuring coherence between the project's digital presence and its overall communication framework.

2. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

SPARC's communication and dissemination strategy is designed to ensure that the project's objectives, activities, and outputs are visible, accessible, clearly understood, and appropriately conveyed to relevant audiences at EU and Member State level. The strategy aims to ensure that SPARC's findings and experiences reach key audiences — including policymakers, healthcare professionals, patient advocacy organisations, and the wider public — in ways that support awareness, understanding, and informed dialogue.

The communication and dissemination strategy supports SPARC's overall aim to facilitate the implementation of personalised cancer medicine by strengthening coordination, promoting alignment with EU initiatives, and contributing to evidence-informed policy discussion. Particular emphasis is placed on communicating the relevance and implications of SPARC activities related to **Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs), liquid biopsy, and disease-specific clinical pilots**, as well as on situating these activities within the broader European policy context.

Recognising that communication needs, stakeholder expectations, and policy priorities evolve over time, the strategy is conceived as a **dynamic and adaptive framework**. Its implementation will be adjusted in light of project progress, stakeholder feedback, policy developments at EU level, and monitoring indicators (e.g. engagement metrics, participation in events, survey responses). Updates will be discussed within WP9 and, where relevant, validated with the Steering Committee to ensure continued relevance, coherence, and impact throughout the project lifecycle. The effectiveness of this Plan will be formally assessed through key project deliverables. In particular, D9.2 (Mid-Term Report on Communication and

Engagement Activities) will provide an opportunity to evaluate progress, analyse engagement indicators, and adjust priorities or tools where needed. Lessons learned will be further consolidated in D9.3 (Final Dissemination and Communication Report) and reflected in D9.4 (Sustainability Strategy), ensuring that communication efforts remain responsive, relevant, and aligned with evolving EU policy discussions throughout the project lifecycle.

2.1 Objectives

The main objectives of SPARC's communication and dissemination strategy are to:

- **Increase awareness** of SPARC's objectives, scope, and contribution to the implementation of personalised cancer medicine in Europe, with a focus on Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs), liquid biopsy, and disease-specific pilot activities;
- **Communicate project progress and outputs** in a clear, accurate, and timely manner to relevant audiences at EU and Member State level;
- **Support alignment and coherence** between SPARC activities, the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine (JA PCM), and other relevant EU and national initiatives, by ensuring consistency in messaging, timing, and framing of communication outputs;
- **Disseminate results** in accessible, relevant, and timely formats that facilitate uptake, replication, and informed use in policy, planning, and implementation contexts, including within the framework of the JA PCM;
- **Promote understanding** of MTBs, liquid biopsy, and relevant technical aspects emerging from disease-specific pilot activities, at an appropriate level for different audiences;
- **Facilitate the uptake and use of SPARC outputs** in policy, planning, and implementation contexts by presenting information in policy-relevant and accessible formats;
- **Ensure transparency** regarding SPARC's activities, processes and results.

Strategic Focus Areas for Communication

SPARC's communication and dissemination activities are structured around the following strategic focus areas:

I. Positioning and Identity within the EU Cancer Policy Landscape

Establishing a clear, strong, and recognisable project identity that reflects SPARC's role as a coordination and support action contributing to the implementation of personalised cancer medicine in Europe. Particular emphasis is placed on positioning SPARC in a complementary and enabling relationship with EU-level

initiatives, including the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine, while avoiding duplication and reinforcing coherence across the policy landscape.

II. Thematic Focus on MTBs, Liquid Biopsy, and Clinical Pilots

Communicating the relevance and implications of SPARC activities related to MTBs, liquid biopsy, and disease-specific pilots, highlighting their potential contribution to improved cancer care pathways and policy development.

III. Audience-Sensitive Messaging

Adapting communication narratives to the perspectives and needs of different target audiences, including policymakers, healthcare professionals, patient organisations, patients and citizens and the wider personalised cancer medicine community.

IV. Multi-Channel Engagement

Using an integrated mix of online and offline channels — including the project website, social media, publications, on-site events, and webinars — to reach target audiences where they are.

V. Evidence- and Experience-Based Communication

Communicating project progress and outputs in a way that reflects implementation experiences, emerging insights, and lessons learned from SPARC activities.

VI. Transparency and Accessibility

Ensuring that communication is open, accurate, inclusive and accessible, supporting understanding of SPARC's objectives, scope, and relevance among both specialised and non-specialised audiences.

Alignment with SPARC's Overall Aim

This communication and dissemination strategy supports SPARC's overarching aim to facilitate the implementation of personalised cancer medicine in Europe by:

- Creating visibility for SPARC's scientific achievements as well as coordination, policy, and implementation-oriented activities;
- Reinforcing alignment with EU-level initiatives, including the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine, by structuring communication outputs in ways that support coherence, mutual awareness, and policy-relevant exchange;
- Supporting informed policy dialogue through clear, relevant, and accessible communication;
- Enabling awareness, understanding and cross-sector conversations among key stakeholders involved in policy, planning, and implementation.
- Supporting capacity building through outreach, education, and knowledge transfer.

Alignment with the Grant Agreement and action-level indicators

SPARC’s communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement strategy is directly aligned with the objectives and action-level indicators defined in the Grant Agreement (GA, Section 3.2). The strategy adopts a comprehensive, multi-channel and audience-tailored approach designed to maximise visibility, foster stakeholder engagement, and support implementation and policy uptake, while ensuring recognition of EU funding and its added value.

In line with the GA, communication activities are conceived as a progressive pathway from awareness-raising to engagement and action. This pathway supports structured interaction with the JA PCM, involvement of stakeholder organisations and individuals across categories and age groups, reach to defined target groups through awareness activities, and participation in training, workshops, and high-visibility meetings.

The action-level indicators and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the GA provide the reference framework for planning, monitoring, and adapting communication and dissemination activities throughout the project duration.

2.2 Target Audiences

SPARC’s communication and dissemination activities address a set of target audiences that are relevant for policy development, healthcare implementation, professional practice, and public awareness in the field of personalised cancer medicine.

The table below outlines the main audiences and explains their relevance to SPARC.

Target audience	Explanation / relevance for SPARC
EU-level policymakers, institutions and initiatives	Actors responsible for EU health, cancer, research, and data policies. SPARC communication targets this audience to support policy dialogue and alignment, particularly on the role of Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs), liquid biopsy, and disease-specific pilots, and to ensure coherence with EU initiatives such as the JA PCM.
National and regional health authorities	Authorities responsible for cancer policy, health system planning, and implementation at Member State level. Communication focuses on the relevance of SPARC experiences for national implementation,

	governance considerations, and the transferability of pilot insights across different healthcare contexts.
Healthcare professionals and clinical communities	Clinicians and healthcare professionals involved in cancer care delivery and adoption of innovative diagnostics and care pathways. SPARC communication aims to convey the practical and organisational relevance of MTBs, liquid biopsy, and pilot activities at a high level.
Medical and professional associations	Organisations that influence professional standards, guidelines, and best practices. SPARC communication supports awareness of pilot findings and policy-relevant insights that may inform professional dialogue and guideline development.
Patient advocacy organisations and umbrella networks	Organisations representing patient perspectives, access concerns, and equity considerations. Communication aims to highlight the patient-relevant implications of SPARC activities, including impacts on care pathways, access, and prevention strategies.
Research and innovation initiatives	EU-funded projects and initiatives active in cancer, diagnostics, and personalised medicine. SPARC communication supports alignment, complementarity, and mutual visibility within the broader European research and innovation ecosystem.
General public and media	Broader audiences involved in shaping public awareness and understanding of cancer innovation. Communication focuses on high-level information about personalised cancer medicine, innovation in diagnostics, and the objectives and relevance of SPARC.

Table 1: Overview of the SPARC target audiences explained

The relative emphasis placed on different audiences may evolve over the course of the project, reflecting implementation milestones, emerging needs, and policy developments.

2.3 Key Messages and Narrative

SPARC's communication and dissemination activities are guided by a coherent narrative that reflects the project's role as a coordination and support action for personalised cancer medicine implementation.

Key messages underpinning SPARC communication include:

- SPARC supports the implementation of personalised cancer medicine by strengthening coordination and alignment across EU and Member State levels.
- SPARC will develop enabling frameworks to facilitate and accelerate implementation efforts in personalised cancer medicine, providing structured guidance, and tools to support uptake across diverse health systems.
- SPARC contributes to the identification of practical challenges, needs, and pathways related to diagnostics, care delivery, and access in personalised cancer medicine.
- SPARC complements existing EU initiatives, including the JA PCM, without duplicating their activities.
- SPARC supports evidence-informed and value-based policy dialogue by synthesising insights emerging from pilot activities, coordination efforts, and implementation work.
- SPARC aims to improve coherence and consistency in approaches to personalised cancer medicine across diverse national contexts.

These messages are adapted in tone and emphasis depending on the audience and communication context, while maintaining consistency in substance. Communication outputs are designed to be accurate, balanced, and policy-relevant, supporting understanding and informed use by decision-makers and other relevant stakeholders. SPARC's narrative is conveyed not only through written outputs, but also through curated communication formats such as interviews and surveys published in connection with key project moments, which help contextualise SPARC's work and amplify its relevance for policy and implementation audiences

Audience-Tailored Messaging Approach

While SPARC is guided by a coherent set of overarching key messages, communication outputs are systematically tailored to reflect the priorities, level of technical expertise, and decision-making context of each target audience.

In practice:

- **For EU-level policymakers and institutions**, messaging emphasises governance implications, alignment with EU initiatives (including the JA PCM),

roadmap relevance, and the contribution of SPARC insights to structured policy dialogue and coordination.

- **For national and regional health authorities**, communication highlights implementation experiences, transferability of pilot insights, organisational implications of MTBs and liquid biopsy integration, and practical considerations related to sustainability and system readiness.
- **For healthcare professionals and clinical communities**, messaging focuses on operational relevance, workflow implications, clinical coordination aspects, and high-level synthesis of implementation lessons emerging from pilots.
- **For patient organisations and civil society**, communication adopts accessible and culturally adopted language and emphasises equity, access, care pathways, and patient-centred implications of personalised cancer medicine implementation.
- **For research and innovation initiatives**, messaging highlights complementarity, cross-project learning, and opportunities for coordination and knowledge exchange.

This audience-sensitive adaptation ensures that SPARC communication remains coherent in substance while being contextually relevant and meaningful to each stakeholder group.

2.4 Communication Channels and Tools

SPARC will use a combination of digital, written, and event-based channels to support communication and engagement throughout the project. Channels are selected to ensure accessibility, proportionality, and appropriateness for different audiences, while maintaining consistency and relevance of messaging. This chapter provides an overview of the communication channels and tools used across the project. These channels are applied in different ways depending on the communication objective and audience.

The main communication channels and their intended use include:

- **Project website** - The project website will act as the central communication hub, providing clear and accessible information on the project's objectives, structure, timeline, and activities. It will be regularly updated with news, reports, and deliverables. It supports transparency, participation, and access to project results for a wide range of audiences.
- **Social Media Platforms** - Dedicated project accounts on selected social media platforms (X, LinkedIn, YouTube) will be used selectively to share information, promote participation opportunities, and increase visibility of project activities and outputs, in complementarity with more structured communication and dissemination formats. These platforms will allow for real-time engagement with

diverse audiences, including researchers, policymakers, and patient organizations.

- **Newsletters** - Project newsletters regularly published on the website, shared on social media and with the partners through Basecamp, providing updates on project progress, deliverables, and upcoming events.
- **Press releases** - Press releases are used as a targeted media outreach tool to communicate key milestones and significant developments of the project to a broader audience, including specialised health and policy media, and made available on the project website.
- **Events** - SPARC will leverage both project-organised and existing external events (e.g. conferences, workshops, meetings) as communication channels, supporting dialogue, visibility, and exchange with relevant stakeholder communities. Project results will be presented at national and international scientific conferences, congresses, and public health forums.
- **Peer-reviewed publications** - Results and findings from the project will be published in peer-reviewed journals to ensure that they reach the scientific community and contribute to advancing cancer research and treatment. Where possible, lay abstracts or plain-language summaries of scientific publications will be produced and made available through the project website and communication channels to support understanding among patients, caregivers, policymakers, and the wider public.
- **Partner networks and channels** - Project updates and key messages will be amplified through dissemination via partners' websites, newsletters, and existing networks. This will include (re-)posting reports, deliverables, and news updates on relevant external platforms.
- **Communication materials** - A range of materials (e.g. interviews, summaries, visual content) will be developed using accessible language to support communication across audiences.

The visual presentation of relevant channels, including illustrative screenshots, examples of communication materials, and technical elements (such as templates), are provided in Chapter 6.

2.5 Central role of patient organisations

Equally central to SPARC's overall communication and stakeholder engagement approach is the **strong and meaningful involvement of patient organisations**. Patient groups contribute essential experience-based evidence, highlight unmet needs, and ensure that all SPARC outputs - ranging from clinical pathways and diagnostic workflows to training materials and policy recommendations - reflect real patient priorities and lived realities.

Patient perspectives are embedded throughout SPARC's governance and engagement architecture, from pilot-level feedback and internal reflection to expert-level validation and broader stakeholder dialogue. Patient organisations are involved where relevant through coordination with WP7 in structured engagement formats, expert discussions, and dissemination activities, ensuring that considerations related to equity, trust, communication, and acceptability are integrated across all phases of the project.

This approach guarantees that SPARC remains human-centred, equitable, and responsive to the needs of people affected by cancer, while also strengthening the relevance and legitimacy of its policy-oriented outputs.

3. Internal Communication and Insight Extraction

Within SPARC, communication is understood not only as an external visibility function, but as a core internal coordination mechanism that **supports alignment, learning, and policy readiness across Work Packages and pilot activities**. Internal communication structures are deliberately designed to enable the continuous circulation of information, emerging insights, and implementation challenges between technical teams, stakeholder engagement activities, and policy-oriented outputs.

This approach reflects SPARC's role as a support and coordination action, where value is generated through synthesis, translation, and alignment. Internal communication activities therefore play a critical role in ensuring coherence across pilots, consistency of messaging, and timely identification of issues relevant for policy uptake.

The proposed formats serve as the **primary entry point for bottom-up insight generation**. They are **intentionally lightweight, low-barrier, and embedded within existing project workflows** to avoid consultation fatigue and to maximise participation across Work Packages.

For this reason, in addition to participation in regular consortium meetings to support alignment and relevant external events to capture insights aligned with the project's scope, key formats include:

- **Open Office sessions** (1 hour per month, online, moderated by EAPM) provide an informal and accessible space for consortium partners to raise questions, flag emerging challenges, and request targeted support across Work Packages. These sessions support early detection of implementation challenges and facilitate horizontal learning within the consortium.
- **Insight Extraction moments** (approximately one per month, aligned with consortium meetings, events, or key project milestones), systematically

integrated into Work Package meetings, workshops, and project milestones. These moments are used by EAPM/WP9 to capture emerging trends, recurring challenges, and cross-cutting observations in a structured way (for example with targeted short live polls), without creating additional standalone meetings.

- **Focused consultations and short expert exchanges**, convened when specific issues require deeper exploration or validation (online, moderated by EAPM). These formats enable targeted reflection on well-defined questions and support rapid clarification of assumptions or emerging findings.

Insights collected through these internal communication mechanisms are documented and synthesised within WP9, and progressively consolidated into:

- structured summaries and internal briefing notes;
- thematic syntheses linked to MTBs, liquid biopsy, and training activities;
- inputs for expert reports, stakeholder engagement outputs, and policy-oriented dissemination, as it will be discussed in more details in Chapter 5.

In addition to live interaction formats, SPARC internal communication is supported by:

- a shared **internal collaboration platform**, managed under WP1 and used to circulate key updates, share summaries and synthesis notes emerging from internal exchanges, and provide a common reference space for materials relevant to communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities.
- a **communication and dissemination activity tracker**, maintained by EAPM and shared regularly with the consortium to support reporting and awareness of activities track.

The combination of these formats supports transparency, reduces information silos, and enables partners to remain informed and engaged with emerging insights, independently of their direct participation in specific meetings.

4. External Communication and Dissemination Activities

SPARC implements a structured approach to external communication and dissemination in order to ensure visibility of the project, support understanding of its objectives and activities to different stakeholders, and facilitate the dissemination of outputs relevant to policy and implementation of personalised cancer medicine.

All the activities build on a set of core communication channels and visibility actions established at project level and are progressively adapted to reflect project milestones,

outputs, and policy-relevant developments and are aligned with the communication objectives and key messages defined in Section 2.

4.1 General Communication Activities (applicable to all target audiences)

SPARC will implement broad-reaching communication efforts aimed at ensuring **general visibility, recognition, and awareness** of the project. These activities are designed to inform a wide range of audiences about SPARC's objectives, scope, progress, and key milestones, and to situate the project within the broader European personalised cancer medicine landscape.

Key tactics include:

- publishing general project updates, milestones, selected outputs and general visibility content through accessible and appropriate communication channels;
- ensuring consistent presentation of SPARC's identity, objectives, and messaging across communication activities;
- promoting visibility of SPARC through participation in relevant events, meetings, and speaking opportunities.
- developing communication content based on project surveys and interviews conducted in the context of SPARC activities and key project milestones (e.g. kick-off meeting, workshops), including the publication of selected interviews and insights through digital channels such as the SPARC YouTube page.

The project website, newsletter, social media accounts and open-access repository will be used as main channels in a coordinated manner to ensure consistency of messaging, visibility of project activities, and accessibility of SPARC outputs for different audiences. Where appropriate, additional channels such as partner's websites, newsletters, and social media accounts will be used to support amplification of SPARC communication activities.

4.2 Targeted Dissemination Activities (applicable to specific audiences)

To complement general external communication activities, SPARC implements targeted outreach and dissemination activities tailored to specific audiences. These activities aim **to ensure that SPARC's objectives, progress, and emerging outputs are communicated in ways that are relevant to different policy, implementation, and professional contexts.**

Target audience	Tactics	Channels
EU-level policymakers, institutions and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of SPARC updates and emerging outputs relevant to EU-level policy discussions Communication aligned with milestones of the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine and related initiatives Visibility through participation in EU-level meetings and policy-oriented events, and cross-initiative exchanges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Newsletter Social media EU-level conferences and policy events Press releases
National and regional health authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of information on SPARC pilot activities, implementation experiences, and lessons learned Communication of governance- and implementation-relevant insights related to diagnostics, care pathways, and access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Newsletter Targeted dissemination via partner channels Relevant national and EU-level events
Healthcare professionals and clinical communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of accessible information on SPARC's scope and areas of focus Communication of high-level clinical and organisational insights emerging from pilot and implementation work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Social media Conferences and professional meetings Partner channels
Medical and professional associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication of pilot findings and policy-relevant insights that may inform professional dialogue and guideline development Visibility of SPARC activities relevant to standards of care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Newsletter Social media Partner and association channels Conferences and professional meetings
Patient advocacy organisations and umbrella networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication of SPARC objectives and patient-relevant implications in accessible language Visibility of activities related to care pathways, access, and equity considerations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Newsletter Social media Partner and umbrella organisation channels

<p>Research and innovation initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-promotion of activities and outputs where relevant • Communication of SPARC scope, progress, and alignment opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Social media • Joint or clustered dissemination opportunities
<p>General public and media</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-level communication on SPARC objectives, innovation in personalised cancer medicine, and the relevance of MTBs and liquid biopsy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amplification of key project messages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Social media • Interviews and video content • Press releases

Table 2: Overview of Targeted Outreach Activities

Notes on scope and consistency

- Targeted outreach activities are **dissemination-focused**, not participatory.
- Structured dialogue and coordination mechanisms are covered in more details in Chapter 5.
- Tactics and channels are adapted over time in line with project progress and emerging outputs.
- Where relevant, dissemination activities will be coordinated in timing and framing with the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine to maximise coherence, visibility, and policy relevance, while respecting the distinct mandates and governance of each initiative.

Together, these external communication and dissemination activities create the conditions for structured policy uptake, which is further addressed in the following chapter through the lens of policy interaction, stakeholder engagement, and contribution to EU-level coordination processes.

5. From Communication to Policy Uptake

5.1 Stakeholder Engagement Rationale

SPARC’s stakeholder engagement approach aims to bring together the full diversity of actors required to support the implementation of personalised cancer medicine across Europe. Stakeholder engagement within SPARC is intentionally designed as a **structural component of the project** and is fully integrated with communication, dissemination, and policy-oriented work.

The framework is built to interconnect **bottom-up insights** emerging from clinical pilots, patient-facing activities, and national implementation realities with **top-down**

strategic coordination at EU level, notably through the Synergy with the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine (JA PCM). This creates a dual-flow system: SPARC generates ground-level evidence, experiential knowledge, and practical solutions, while JA PCM provides overarching policy alignment, coherence, and EU-level strategic direction. Together, these two dimensions reinforce each other, ensuring that real-world challenges inform European policy dialogue and that EU frameworks are translated back into implementable, patient-centred actions.

Stakeholder engagement within SPARC therefore serves a dual purpose: it supports the **co-creation and validation of project outputs**, and it ensures that these outputs are positioned in a way that facilitates coordination, uptake, and sustainability beyond the lifetime of the project.

5.2 Stakeholder Engagement Framework

To operationalise this approach, SPARC applies a **three-level stakeholder engagement architecture** that structures how stakeholder input is generated, consolidated, and translated into policy-relevant outputs. This model ensures that the internal communication activities presented in Chapter 3 are directly linked to **decision-relevant discussion**, rather than remaining siloed within individual Work Packages.

Each level fulfils a distinct function while remaining closely interconnected with the others, as detailed below.

Alignment Group

The Alignment Group represents SPARC's highest-level coordination mechanism, linking the project with major European initiatives and policy structures.

Objective

To ensure that SPARC's activities and outputs are aligned with EU-wide policy priorities, complementary initiatives, and existing frameworks in personalised medicine and cancer care.

Purpose

The Alignment Group acts as a strategic coordination board facilitating dialogue between SPARC and EU-level entities, including the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine, Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, EUnetCCC, CCI4EU, and relevant European Commission bodies. Through this function, it supports coherence across initiatives, avoids duplication, and ensures that SPARC's innovations contribute meaningfully to broader European objectives.

Expected

outcome

A coherent policy environment in which SPARC’s recommendations, tools, and best practices can be integrated into EU-level strategies and coordination processes. The Alignment Group ensures that SPARC’s advances feed into European policy agendas, while developments at EU level inform SPARC’s ongoing work.

Stakeholder Coordination Group (SCG)

The Stakeholder Coordination Group functions as SPARC’s **expert-level engine**, bringing together strategic stakeholders from across the personalised cancer medicine ecosystem.

Figure 2: Composition of the Stakeholder Coordination Group

Objective

To translate insights from pilots, consultations, and engagement activities into structured recommendations and policy-relevant outputs.

Purpose

The SCG serves as the central forum for multidisciplinary expert dialogue. Through regular meetings and workshops, it reviews evidence, identifies barriers and enablers, and refines guidance materials. Its composition - spanning clinicians, regulators, HTA bodies, patient organisations, policymakers, and industry representatives - ensures balanced and comprehensive input across technical, regulatory, and implementation perspectives.

Expected

outcome

Consensus-driven recommendations validated by experts across sectors. These recommendations inform SPARC’s policy outputs, influence training and clinical workflows, and provide a foundation for adoption, scaling, and transferability across Member States.

Stakeholder Forum (SForum)

The Stakeholder Forum provides SPARC's open and inclusive space for broad public and professional engagement.

Objective

To gather broad-based feedback, share knowledge, and disseminate pilot learnings to a wide audience, including citizens, civil society organisations, healthcare professionals, national groups, and NGOs. In the first year of the project, the SForum will take the form of a dedicated workshop focusing on patient needs and experience in personalised cancer medicine.

Purpose

The SForum supports dialogue, co-creation, and health literacy by creating a structured space for exchanging best practices, identifying national and local challenges, and strengthening awareness of the value of personalised cancer medicine. It complements expert-level discussions by ensuring transparency and inclusiveness.

Expected

outcome

An annual SForum Report summarising diverse perspectives and experience-based insights. This report feeds into SPARC's internal reflection and dissemination activities, supports EU-level communication, and contributes to uptake at national and regional level.

5.3 Integration with communication and dissemination activities

Across all three levels, stakeholder engagement is closely linked with SPARC's communication and dissemination activities presented in Chapters 3 and 4. Where relevant, consolidated insights collected through the internal communication mechanisms are channelled into the Stakeholder Coordination Group for expert validation, shared with the Alignment Group to support strategic coherence, or reflected in Stakeholder Forum discussions and dissemination outputs. On the other side, inputs generated through these engagement mechanisms are synthesised and communicated in formats appropriate to different audiences, with EAPM/WP9 ensuring consistency and traceability across levels and continuity between dialogue, expert validation, and policy-oriented dissemination.

This integrated framework ensures that stakeholder engagement within SPARC is **systematic, purposeful, and policy-relevant**, directly supporting the project's objectives.

5.4 Alignment and Coordination with JA PCM

The SPARC stakeholder engagement framework is explicitly designed to operationalise the structured synergy established with the JA PCM, as defined in the joint Deliverable D1.2 “Report I on synergies between JA PCM and SPARC”.

This synergy, mandated by the European Commission, is structured around three pillars: (1) integration of patient perspectives, (2) thematic Working Groups on Liquid Biopsy & NGS, Molecular Tumour Boards, and Education & Training, and (3) a coordinated stakeholder engagement, communication, and dissemination strategy.

Within this framework, SPARC contributes both implementation-driven insights and structured communication outputs to support coherence at EU level. Internal synthesis activities, insight extraction mechanisms, and stakeholder consultations generate evidence and experiential feedback that are progressively translated into formats compatible with JA PCM coordination structures. At the same time, communication and dissemination activities are aligned to ensure consistent messaging, mutual visibility, and complementary outreach across initiatives.

As outlined in Deliverable D1.2, coordination between SPARC and JA PCM includes:

- Regular alignment exchanges between coordination teams;
- Participation in joint Working Groups addressing Liquid Biopsy & NGS, MTB harmonisation, and Education & Training;
- A shared stakeholder engagement and communication approach designed to avoid duplication, ensure complementarity, and maximise reach across professional and policy audiences.

Communication and dissemination alignment

Beyond governance coordination, synergy is also reflected in communication practices. This includes:

- Alignment of key messages to ensure consistent terminology and framing of personalised cancer medicine implementation challenges;
- Cross-visibility between SPARC and JA PCM through references on websites, event participation, and joint sessions where appropriate;
- Coordination of dissemination timing, particularly for outputs relevant to roadmap development, policy dialogue, and implementation guidance;
- Participation in shared platforms and EU-level policy discussions, including PCM Cluster and related coordination structures.

SPARC communication outputs — such as policy briefs, thematic syntheses, stakeholder reports, and event-based dissemination — are structured to complement

JA PCM activities, particularly where pilot-generated evidence can inform broader roadmap development. Conversely, JA PCM strategic priorities and evolving coordination frameworks provide orientation for SPARC’s synthesis and dissemination planning.

Role of the stakeholder architecture in supporting synergy

The three-level stakeholder framework supports this alignment:

- The Alignment Group (Level 1 in D1.2) ensures high-level coherence with JA PCM governance and broader EU initiatives, positioning SPARC outputs within the evolving European policy landscape.
- The Stakeholder Coordination Group (Level 2 in D1.2) functions as a translation layer, validating and refining SPARC findings before they are channelled into EU-level discussions or dissemination formats.
- The Stakeholder Forum (Level 3 in D1.2) contributes broader ecosystem input and strengthens transparency, amplifying communication reach and reinforcing alignment with EU-level priorities.

Through this integrated structure, SPARC enables a two-way dynamic:

- **Bottom-up flow:** Pilot insights, patient perspectives, mapping exercises, and stakeholder feedback inform JA PCM discussions and Working Group deliberations.
- **Top-down flow:** JA PCM roadmap development, policy priorities, and coordination frameworks guide SPARC’s synthesis, communication focus, and dissemination timing.

By integrating stakeholder engagement, communication, and dissemination alignment within a single structured framework, SPARC ensures that its activities contribute directly to EU-level coordination while maintaining clarity of roles and mandates between the two initiatives.

6. Overview of Communication Materials

This chapter provides an overview of the main communication materials and technical elements developed and used within SPARC to support the communication channels described previously. It serves as an **evidence and reference section**, illustrating how communication activities are implemented in practice and how project messages are presented across different formats and platforms.

6.1. Project Collaboration Platform

Basecamp is used within the SPARC project as an **internal collaboration platform** supporting coordination among consortium partners, including activities related to communication and dissemination. The platform facilitates the exchange of information, collaborative work on documents, and coordination of inputs contributing to communication materials and dissemination activities.

Governance aspects, access rights, and rules for the use of the platform will be defined in Deliverable 1.1 "SPARC management manual" (due by April 2026) and are managed by the Project Coordinator.

Figure 3: Illustrative screenshot of the internal collaboration platform

In addition, a **shared public project folder** is used to provide easy access to selected communication and dissemination resources, including templates, guidance documents, and materials intended for wider reuse by partners. This complementary access layer supports transparency and efficient uptake of shared resources, without replacing internal coordination mechanisms. This is the link to the shared folder: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/14gVbSsMS2uV6WjbQP5K1SqEIJ02JCVQz?usp=sharing>

Figure 4: Illustrative screenshot of the organisation of the public shared folder

6.2. Website

EAPM created and launched the SPARC project website: <https://sparc-project.eu/>.

The website serves as the central public communication platform of the project and acts as the primary point of reference for stakeholders seeking information on SPARC’s objectives, structure, activities, and results. It will progressively reflect milestones, pilot activities, and public outputs. Key sections include project information, pilot descriptions, news updates, policy-related content, and a dedicated area for results and publicly available materials. It also supports visibility of SPARC’s alignment with broader EU initiatives, including the JA PCM. Content updates are coordinated by EAPM in consultation with the Project Coordinator and relevant WP leaders. Further details on the website’s structure and development are provided in Deliverable D9.5.

Figure 5: Illustrative screenshot of the SPARC website

6.3. Templates and visual assets

To ensure consistency and efficiency across communication activities, a template for presentations and one for deliverables have been prepared and are available for all partners of SPARC in a dedicated “Template and Guidelines folder” in the shared public folder.

Deliverable xx – Name
 Deliverable – Version x

Project Acronym	SPARC
Project Title	Support of Personalized medicine Approaches in Cancer
Project Number	101232874

Deliverable Information:

WP	
Deliverable related number	

Figure 6: Illustrative screenshots of deliverable and slide templates

6.4. Newsletter

Every 3-4 months a newsletter release is planned during the complete duration of the project. Newsletters represent informative, compact and engaging ways of communication traditionally well received by the professionals within the SPARC network and contribute significantly to increasing the visibility of the project.

EAPM is responsible for the preparation, content creation, and distribution of the newsletter. Each issue is published on the project website, promoted through SPARC’s social media channels, and shared with consortium partners via email. In addition, newsletters are stored in a dedicated folder within the shared public project repository, ensuring easy access, reuse, and long-term availability of past issues for partners and external stakeholders.

Key Messages:

- SPARC launches as Europe’s key implementation engine for personalised cancer medicine.
- Seven clinical pilots will drive real-world integration of liquid biopsy and NGS.
- A European MTB blueprint will support consistent, scalable decision-making.
- Digital tools, training and equity frameworks will strengthen health-system readiness.
- SPARC aligns directly with the Joint Action on PCM, the EU Life Sciences Strategy, the Biotech Act, the AI Act and the Draghi Report.
- The Stakeholder Coordination Group “connects the dots” between EU, national, regional and civil society actors.
- SPARC supports Europe’s competitiveness, innovation capacity and long-term Health Union agenda.

Get in Contact:

Manuel Ottaviano, Project Coordinator
manuel.ottaviano@upm.es

Chiara de Tomasso, Communication Officer
chiara.de.tomasso@euapm.eu

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Figure 7: Illustrative screenshots of the Newsletter #1 of December 2025

6.5. Social Media Accounts

Dedicated project accounts have been established on selected social media platforms to support visibility, engagement, and dissemination of SPARC activities and outputs.

LinkedIn is the primary social media platform for the project. It is used as the main channel to share project updates, highlight milestones, promote events and participation opportunities, and disseminate selected outputs. Posts are published regularly (approximately once per week).

X is used to mirror selected content published on LinkedIn, supporting additional visibility and outreach where relevant. The consortium is currently reflecting on the most appropriate microblogging platform for the project (including potential alternatives such as Bluesky), and the use of X will be kept proportionate to its reach and engagement.

YouTube is used to host audiovisual content produced within the project. At the current stage, the channel includes approximately 15 interviews recorded during the project kick-off meeting. Additional interviews with project partners and contributors will be recorded throughout the project duration to capture insights and perspectives as SPARC progresses. Video content hosted on YouTube is also disseminated through LinkedIn and, where relevant, mirrored on X to maximise visibility.

Together, these platforms complement more structured communication and engagement activities by supporting ongoing visibility, accessibility of content, and cross-channel dissemination.

Links:

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/sparc-eu/>

X: https://x.com/sparc_eu?s=21

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@SPARC-EU>

SPARC.eu

EU4Health project advancing equitable and sustainable personalised cancer medicine across Europe.
Biotechnology Research · 161 followers · 11-50 employees

Figure 8: Illustrative screenshots of the social media accounts

6.6. Zenodo SPARC community

SPARC uses an open-access Zenodo community to ensure long-term visibility, accessibility, and reuse of selected project outputs, including deliverables, reports, policy briefs, and dissemination materials. This repository supports transparency, open science principles, and ensures that SPARC outputs are not only disseminated during the project, but also preserved and made reusable for stakeholders, policymakers, and the wider research and professional community.

To support consistent and harmonized use of the repository across the consortium, a short internal how-to guide has been prepared for project partners. This guide provides practical instructions on how to upload materials to the SPARC Zenodo community, including basic metadata requirements, versioning considerations, and alignment with SPARC’s communication and dissemination practices. The guide is shared internally via the project’s internal collaboration channels, including Basecamp and the shared public project folder to ensure easy access and uptake.

The SPARC Zenodo community is publicly accessible at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sparc-project/records>

Figure 9: Illustrative screenshot of the SPARC Zenodo community and the upload guide shared with the consortium partners

7. Planning

Communication and dissemination activities within SPARC are **aligned with the overall project timeline, with the action-level indicators defined in the Grant Agreement and adapted to the maturity of project activities and outputs**. A phased approach is adopted to ensure that communication initially supports visibility and awareness, and progressively fosters engagement, participation, and action-oriented involvement through workshops, stakeholder fora, training activities, and high-visibility meetings.

Considering that this deliverable will be updated at Month 18, the present version outlines an overall vision of communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities for the full project duration, while providing a more detailed and operational plan for 2026, corresponding to the first 18 months of implementation. Planning remains flexible and will be refined as project activities progress and additional inputs are received from consortium partners. EAPM will support this coordination through the regular exchange and the use of shared planning and tracking tools presented in Chapter 3, allowing planned activities to be monitored and adjusted as needed.

7.1. Phased approach to communication and dissemination

Early phase: visibility, positioning, and ecosystem mapping (ongoing)

During the early phase of the project, communication activities focus on:

- establishing SPARC's identity and positioning within the European personalised cancer medicine landscape;
- raising awareness of the project's objectives, scope, and structure;
- mapping and connecting with relevant stakeholders, initiatives, and networks at EU and Member State level.

As of February 2026, several key actions have already been implemented, including the launch and population of the project website, activation of social media channels, initial newsletter dissemination, and visibility actions linked to the project kick-off and early coordination meetings, within the SPARC consortium and with JA PCM. At this stage, the project's YouTube channel already hosts approximately 15 videos (interviews recorded during the kick-off meeting in Madrid).

Mid-phase: insight sharing, validation, and interim synthesis

As project activities progress and implementation experience accumulates, communication and dissemination efforts increasingly focus on:

- sharing emerging insights and lessons learned from pilot activities and coordination work;
- supporting validation and discussion of interim findings through targeted dissemination and stakeholder engagement formats;
- facilitating cross-project learning and alignment with JA PCM.

This phase places greater emphasis on thematic communication, expert-oriented dissemination, and interim synthesis outputs, while maintaining ongoing general visibility. During this phase, communication and dissemination activities increasingly contribute to action-level indicators related to stakeholder involvement, training participation, and structured engagement formats, as defined in the Grant Agreement.

Final phase: consolidated results, policy uptake, and legacy

In the final phase of the project, communication and dissemination activities prioritise:

- dissemination of consolidated results, recommendations, and policy-relevant outputs;
- support for policy dialogue, uptake, and transferability at EU and Member State level;
- ensuring the sustainability and accessibility of SPARC outputs beyond the project lifetime.

Activities in this phase include targeted policy-oriented dissemination, final synthesis publications, and structured communication around legacy resources. This phase primarily contributes to action-level indicators related to policy uptake, high-visibility meetings, and sustained stakeholder reach, consolidating SPARC's contribution beyond the project lifetime.

7.2. Calendar of Events

SPARC's communication and dissemination planning includes participation in, and organisation of, events at EU and international level that are relevant to personalised cancer medicine, diagnostics, oncology, and health policy. Participation in events serves multiple, complementary purposes and is adapted to the nature of the event, the maturity of project outputs, and the intended audience.

Event-related activities may include:

- **Scientific and professional dissemination**, through the presentation of SPARC results and experiences by consortium partners in the form of oral

presentations, panel contributions, or poster sessions, where appropriate and in line with the scope of the event;

- **Visibility and outreach activities**, such as the presence of SPARC through dedicated desks, booths, or informational materials at major conferences and meetings, with the aim of increasing awareness of the project, its objectives, and its role within the European personalised cancer medicine landscape;
- **Organisation of SPARC-led events or sessions**, including workshops, side events, or policy-oriented sessions hosted within larger conferences or meetings. These activities provide structured opportunities to discuss implementation challenges, policy implications, and coordination needs, and may include dedicated policy sessions designed and organised by the project. Workshop #1, planned for 2026, will constitute the first SForum of the project. In Year 1, the SForum will take the form of a dedicated workshop focusing on patient needs in personalised cancer medicine implementation (). In line with the Grant Agreement, the workshop will contribute to action-level indicators related to stakeholder engagement, implementation support, and high-visibility meetings, while generating input to inform subsequent stakeholder and policy-oriented activities.

Target messages, stakeholder segmentation, and detailed objectives will be further refined based on early pilot insights and internal synthesis activities, and will be fully specified in the updated version of this deliverable at Month 18.

The following indicative calendar for the first year includes both **completed and planned activities** and is updated iteratively over the course of the project to reflect emerging opportunities, confirmed outputs, and alignment with relevant policy processes, including those linked to the JA PCM with which joint participation to selected events is also foreseen.

- **SPARC kick off meeting** (November 2025, Madrid) [concluded]
- **JA PCM kick off meeting** (January 2026, Bruxelles) - participation and visibility [concluded]
- **ISLB workshop** (May 2026, Pompeii) - participation and visibility
- **SIOPEAC Europe Annual Meeting** (May 2026, Glasgow) - visibility
- **Stakeholder Forum** (July 2026, online) - SPARC-led workshop on patient needs (Year 1 SForum)
- **EAPM policy event** (September 2026, Bruxelles) - SPARC-led session
- **ESP** (September 2026, Stockholm) - participation, visibility and possible SPARC-led session
- **ESMO** (October 2026, Madrid) - participation, visibility and possible SPARC-led session
- **SPARC annual meeting** (October or November 2026, TBD)
- **ISLB annual conference** (November 2026, Madrid) - possible participation

For the subsequent years of the project, SPARC will target **similar types of scientific, professional, and policy-oriented events**, with participation and organisation of activities adapted in response to project progress, invitations received, and strategic dissemination opportunities aligned with emerging outputs and policy needs.

This list reflects current planning and may evolve over time as additional inputs are received from work package leaders and partners. Where relevant, project officers and relevant European Commission services will be informed in advance of public events or events with media visibility.

7.3. Newsletters

Project newsletters are used as a key channel to provide **regular, structured updates** on SPARC activities, progress, and outputs to subscribed audiences.

An **indicative quarterly schedule** is foreseen, aligned with major project milestones and dissemination needs. Newsletter content typically includes:

- highlights of recent project activities;
- updates on pilot progress and emerging insights;
- announcements of upcoming events and opportunities for engagement;
- links to newly published outputs and resources.

Indicative schedule:

- Newsletter #1 – December 2025 (published)
- Newsletter #2 – April 2026
- Newsletter #3 – July 2026
- Newsletter #4 – October 2026

Subsequent newsletters will be planned for 2027–2028, and may be adapted over time to reflect project dynamics and communication priorities.

7.4. Social media activity

Social media activities support continuous visibility, engagement, and amplification of SPARC communication and dissemination efforts. Posting frequency and content formats are adapted to the **intensity of project activity** and the availability of relevant outputs. Formats include short news items, visual content, links to longer publications, and audiovisual materials. Activity levels and formats are reviewed periodically to ensure relevance and effectiveness.

Social media activity includes:

- regular updates highlighting project milestones and events;
- promotion of publications, interviews, videos, and selected outputs;
- amplification of relevant partner and EU-level initiatives where appropriate.

At the current stage of the project:

- posts are published regularly (once or twice per week in the initial phase, to be adapted on the base of number of workshops, events and the response from our partners to ensure that the profiles are always active) on LinkedIn and X;
- audiovisual content is shared via YouTube

The frequency and type of social media content will be adapted over time, taking into account project activities, upcoming events, partner contributions, and audience engagement.

8. Monitoring and Sustainability Plan

This chapter describes how SPARC monitors the effectiveness of its communication and dissemination activities and ensures the sustainability of key outputs beyond the project duration.

8.1. Monitoring and adaptation

The effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities within SPARC will be monitored throughout the project using a **combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators**. Monitoring supports continuous improvement and allows activities to be adapted in response to emerging needs, sensitivities, or opportunities, while remaining aligned with the indicative planning described in Chapter 7.

Monitoring under WP9 will track progress against the action-level indicators defined in the Grant Agreement and focus on performance against planned activities. In addition to operational tracking, WP9 aligns its monitoring framework with the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the GA. These KPIs provide measurable reference points for assessing overall reach, engagement, and dissemination effectiveness, ensuring that communication objectives remain **specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART)**. The main communication-related indicators monitored under WP9 are summarised below.

Channel / Tool	KPI	Indicator / Target
Website	Number of unique visits	≥ 5000

Newsletter	Number of issues published	12
Peer-reviewed publications	Number of scientific publications	As defined in GA
Press Releases	Number of press releases issued	10 during project lifetime
Social media posts and videos	Number of posts and videos referring to SPARC	≥ 500
Dissemination Events (project-organized and external)	Number of events organised or contributed to	As defined in GA
Overall stakeholder engagement (across all channels and consortium activities)	Unique stakeholders reached	≥ 15000 cumulative (project-wide target, as defined in GA)

Table 3: KPIs

Data will be collected through the communication channels and engagement mechanisms already in place and consolidated periodically to support adaptive planning. Key monitoring indicators will include, where relevant:

- **Web and social media analytics**, such as website visits, page views, and follower growth, and interaction metrics (e.g. likes, comments, shares);
- **Event participation data**, including attendance figures and audience composition where available;
- **Qualitative feedback**, collected through stakeholder interactions, surveys, and informal feedback during events and engagement activities.

Monitoring results are **reviewed on a continuous basis** through ongoing coordination formats (Open Office sessions and activity tracking tools, see Chapter 3) **and consolidated periodically** (twice per year) within WP9. These reviews are used to adapt communication approaches, channels, and formats as needed to maximise impact and relevance. Monitoring will also support **early identification of potential communication risks** (e.g. misinterpretation of results or sensitivities related to

vulnerable audiences), allowing mitigation measures to be implemented where needed.

8.2 Sustainability of communication and dissemination activities

SPARC applies a set of measures to support the **long-term accessibility and reuse** of its communication and dissemination outputs beyond the project lifetime.

Key elements include:

- the use of the open-access Zenodo community to ensure long-term preservation, visibility, and reuse of selected project outputs;
- preservation of key website content after project completion, ensuring continued access to core information, outputs, and resources;
- reliance on established stakeholder networks and partnerships to support continued dissemination, uptake, and reference to SPARC results in policy and professional contexts.

Together, these measures ensure that SPARC's communication and dissemination efforts contribute not only to short-term visibility, but also to lasting impact and policy relevance.

9. Conclusions

This Communication and Dissemination Plan establishes a clear, structured, and flexible framework to support SPARC's objectives and maximise the impact of its activities and outputs. By integrating communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement into a coherent strategy, the plan ensures that SPARC's work is visible, well understood, and positioned to inform policy dialogue and implementation at both EU and Member State level.

The plan reflects SPARC's role as a coordination and support action within the European personalised cancer medicine landscape. Communication and dissemination activities are designed not as standalone visibility tools, but as instruments to support coherence, learning, and uptake. Through systematic internal communication and insight extraction, SPARC ensures that implementation experiences and emerging challenges are translated into structured, policy-relevant outputs.

Alignment with the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine and other EU initiatives is embedded throughout the strategy, reinforcing complementarity and avoiding duplication. The stakeholder engagement architecture further strengthens

this approach by connecting bottom-up evidence from pilots and patient perspectives with expert validation and high-level policy coordination.

By applying a phased approach to communication and dissemination, the plan ensures that activities evolve alongside project maturity, shifting from early visibility and positioning to interim synthesis and, ultimately, to consolidated results and policy uptake. Monitoring and sustainability measures support continuous improvement and ensure that SPARC outputs remain accessible and influential beyond the project lifetime.

In conclusion, this plan provides a robust and adaptable foundation for effective communication and dissemination within SPARC, supporting its overarching aim to facilitate the implementation of personalised cancer medicine across Europe and to contribute meaningfully to a coherent and patient-centred European cancer policy framework.